

QUASI STATIC COMPRESSIVE RESPONSE OF CFRP HONEYCOMB WITH PMI FOAM FILLERS

H. Zhou¹, R. Guo², K. Bao³, H. Wei⁴ and R. Liu⁵

¹ School of Mechanical Engineering, Nanjing University of Science and Technology, Nanjing 210094, China, email: hao.zhou@njust.edu.cn

² School of Mechanical Engineering, Nanjing University of Science and Technology, Nanjing 210094, China, email: guorui@njust.edu.cn

³ School of Mechanical Engineering, Nanjing University of Science and Technology, Nanjing 210094, China, email: m15250983237_1@163.com

⁴ School of Mechanical Engineering, Nanjing University of Science and Technology, Nanjing 210094, China, email: 2296818513@qq.com

⁵ School of Mechanical Engineering, Nanjing University of Science and Technology, Nanjing 210094, China, email: liurongz116@163.com

Keywords: CFRP, Honeycomb core, Foam filler, Compressive response, Numerical simulation

ABSTRACT

A hybrid core made from square carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) honeycomb filled with polymethylacrylimide (PMI) foams was proposed and prepared. Quasi static compression tests and numerical simulations were conducted and effects of the geometric parameters and foam fillers on the compressive response and energy absorption of the core were discussed. The results show that the foam fillers significantly improved the compressive properties of the honeycomb and the geometrical parameters affect the compressive response of the core. The research can guide the design and optimization of lightweight and energy efficient core structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures are playing an important role in the protection structures in different engineering realms. As the main part for energy absorption in a sandwich structure, the core has a significant effect on the protective performance of the sandwich. In recent years, lightweight and energy efficient design of the core has drawn the concerns of many researchers.

Fiber reinforced composite materials have been investigated a lot due to their advantages in mechanical properties, i.e. low weight, high specific strength and stiffness, strong corrosion resisting properties and enduring performances, as well as the outstanding designable ability. B P Russell et al[1] fabricated square carbon fiber epoxy matrix composite honeycombs and measured their out-of-plane compressive and in-plane shear responses as a function of relative density. Theoretical predictions of the compressive and shear strength were also conducted. Further research on the quasi static three-point bending behavior and soft impact response of this kind of composite sandwich have also been carried out by B. P. Russell et al[2, 3]. Y Hu et al[4] designed and fabricated a novel carbon fiber reinforced composite lattice truss sandwich panel through mould pressing method, the strength and failure modes of this novel structure were analyzed by compressive and shear tests.

Thin-walled structures filled with low-density foam materials have provided new ideas for lightweight and energy efficient design of sandwich cores. T Y Reddy et al[5] analyzed the effect of low density polyurethane (PU) foam on the axial crushing of thin-walled circular tubes and found that PU foam fillers effectively improved the energy absorption property. C Wu et al[6] improved the mechanical properties of the honeycomb core by rigid PU foam fillers. H Mozafari et al[7] investigated the effect of PU foam fillers on in-plane lateral crushing properties of honeycomb cores and pointed out that the foam fillers significantly increased the core strength and improved the energy absorption capacity. Q Liu et al[8, 9] experimentally studied the effect of Expanded Polypropylene (EPP) foam fillers on the mechanical properties of aluminum honeycombs under quasi-static and dynamic compressive loadings.

PMI foams have a crosslinked, 100% closed cellular structure and the uniform material distribution throughout the cell walls gives excellent structural stability and a high level of mechanical strength, offering the largest potential for manufacturing lightweight sandwich structures with PMI foam core[10]. However, there is limited research on the properties of composite honeycomb cores with PMI foam fillers.

In this paper, a type of hybrid core made up of square CFRP honeycomb and PMI foam fillers was proposed and prepared. Quasi static compression tests and corresponding numerical simulations were conducted. The effect of the geometric parameters and foam strengthen on the compressive response of the core were analyzed.

2 PREPARATION AND QUASI STATIC COMPRESSION TEST

The core proposed in this paper is made up of square honeycomb and foam block fillers. The honeycomb is made from CFRP sheet based on woven carbon fiber cloth with areal density of 200 g/m² and low-viscosity epoxy resin. The properties of the CFRP material were measured by quasi static compression and tensile tests and shown in Table 1.

Property	Value
0/90° elastic modulus	$E_0 = 4.8 \text{ GPa}$
45° elastic modulus	$E_{45} = 6.0 \text{ GPa}$
0° tensile strength	$\sigma_0^t = 195 \text{ MPa}$
0° compressive strength	$\sigma_0^c = 191 \text{ MPa}$
45° tensile strength	$\sigma_{45}^t = 103 \text{ MPa}$
45° compressive strength	$\sigma_{45}^c = 153 \text{ MPa}$
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_h = 0.16$
Density	$\rho_h = 1450 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Table 1 Mechanical properties of woven CFRP material

Three types of PMI foams with different densities were investigated in this study. Details of various foams are given in Table 2

Properties	Foam A	Foam B	Foam C
Density(kg/m ³)	52	75	110
Compressive modulus(MPa)	47	71	119
Compressive strength(MPa)	0.99	2.0	3.0
Tensile modulus(MPa)	74	120	200
Tensile strength(MPa)	1.7	2.6	4.1
Shear modulus(MPa)	23	30	70
Shear strength(MPa)	0.92	1.6	2.7

Table 2 Mechanical properties of PMI foam

Fig. 1 Preparation process of CFRP honeycomb core with foam fillers

The preparation process of the CFRP honeycomb cores with foam fillers is shown in Fig. 1.

(a) The CFRP sheets with the thickness of $t_w=0.4$ mm was prepared via resin transfer molding method and the sheets were cut into rectangular pieces as sketched in Fig. 1(a).

(b) The rectangular pieces were slotted together as shown in Fig. 1(b) to assemble the square honeycomb. The joints between pieces were bounded using a low viscosity epoxy adhesive.

(c) The PMI foams were cut into blocks with the dimension of length and width equal to l_w and height equals to h_c . Then the foam blocks with epoxy resin on the surfaces were inserted into the honeycomb and lastly the assembled core was cured at 60 °C for 2 hours. The prepared core structure with $l_w=10$ mm and $h_c=20$ mm is shown in Fig. 1(d).

The quasi static compression tests were performed via the WAW-300B universal testing machine. To reduce the measuring error caused by frictions, two 3 mm-thick steel plates were adhesively attached to the top and bottom surfaces of the core, respectively. High speed camera was applied to record the compression process of the CFRP honeycomb core with foam fillers.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

3.1 Geometrical model

The FE model of the CFRP honeycomb core with foam fillers under quasi static compressive load was established using ABAQUS 2016, as shown in Fig. 3.

The honeycomb was modelled by four-node shell elements (S4R) while the PMI foam blocks were modelled by eight-node solid elements (C3D8R). The mesh sizes of elements in the honeycomb and foam fillers are both $l_w/10$, which was based on the study of mesh sensitivity effects. Rigid plates were set at the top surface and bottom surface, respectively, and the core was tied to the rigid plates at the interfaces. The bottom plate was fixed while a z -direction displacement was applied on the top plate to simulate the compressive load of which the strain rate is 0.001 s⁻¹.

Fig. 3 FE model of CFRP honeycomb core with foam fillers under quasi static compression (section view)

3.2 Material model

Prior to damage initiation, the CFRP sheet was modelled as an orthotropic elastic material and the elastic response of the undamaged material is given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \gamma_{12} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/E_1 & -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 0 \\ -\nu_{21}/E_2 & 1/E_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/G \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where ε_{11} and ε_{22} are direct strains and γ_{12} is the engineering shear strain. The Young's moduli E_1 and E_2 , along with the shear modulus G and Poisson's ratio ν_{21} are the four relevant elastic constants of the unidirectional lamina while ν_{21} is not an independent elastic constant and related to the other elastic constants via the relation $\nu_{21}=(E_2/E_1)\nu_{12}$.

Damage initiation was modelled using Hashin's failure criteria[11] which takes four failure modes into consideration, namely fiber tension, fiber compression, matrix tension and matrix compression. After damage initiates, a nonlinear stress versus strain response accompanies damage progression due

to a progressive drop in three moduli (E_1 , E_2 and G) with increasing strain is given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \gamma_{12} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/[E_1(1-d_f)] & -\nu_{21}[E_1(1-d_f)(1-d_m)] & 0 \\ -\nu_{12}[E_2(1-d_m)(1-d_f)] & 1/[E_2(1-d_m)] & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/G(1-d_s) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where d_f and d_m are damage variables reflecting the damage state of the fiber and matrix, respectively. Details of the damage evolution law can be referred in [12]

The PMI foam blocks are modelled as crushable foam using hardening curves obtained by compression test on cubic foam samples. The compression process can be described as a linear elastic stage followed by a plastic hardening stage. In the plastic hardening stage, a phenomenological yield surface for a closed-cell foam was proposed by Deshpande et al[13], which is given by:

$$F = \sqrt{q^2 + \alpha^2 \sigma_m^2} - \sigma_{yf} \sqrt{1 + (\alpha/3)^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where σ_{yf} is the uniaxial tensile or compressive yield strength of the foam, q is the Von Mises stress, σ_m is the mean stress, α is a parameter defining the shape of the yield surface, which can be given by:

$$\alpha = 3k/\sqrt{9-k^2} \quad (4)$$

where $k = \sigma_{cf}^0/p_{cf}^0$, which is the ratios of the initial uniaxial yield stress σ_{cf}^0 to the hydrostatic compressive yield stress p_{cf}^0 .

Based on the yield stress in hydrostatic compression, the evolution of the shape of the yield surface can be described as:

$$p_{cf}(\varepsilon_{vol}^{pl}) = \frac{\sigma_{cf}(\varepsilon_{vol}^{pl}) \left[\sigma_{cf}(\varepsilon_{axial}^{pl}) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha^2+9} \right) + \frac{P_{tf}}{3} \right]}{p_{tf} + \sigma_{cf}(\varepsilon_{axial}^{pl})/3} \quad (5)$$

where ε_{vol}^{pl} is the plastic volumetric strain and p_{tf} is the hydrostatic tensile yield stress.

3.3 Comparison between experimental and numerical results

The numerical and experimental results were compared for the validation of the FE model. Fig. 4 shows the nominal stress versus nominal strain curves of the core with $l_w=10$ mm, $h_c=20$ mm and $\rho_f=75$ kg/m³, obtained from the compressive test and numerical simulation, respectively.

Fig. 4 Comparison of nominal stress(σ_n) versus nominal strain(ε_n) curves of the core with $l_w=10$ mm and $\rho_f=75$ kg/m³ between experimental and numerical results

We can see from Fig. 4 that the compressive response of the hybrid core when the nominal strain is less than 0.15 can be divided into four stages defined as I) linear elastic stage, II)

failure stage and IV) plateau stage. σ_n - ε_n curves of the core obtained from the compression test and numerical simulation agree quite well, indicating that the FE model can predict the four stages of the compressive response of the core in a reasonable accuracy. Nominal stress in the plateau stage of the numerical results was larger than that of the experimental results. The reason the discrepancy is that the cohesive bonding between the honeycomb and foam fillers was treated as perfect bonding in the FE model for simplification. Despite this, the FE model is accurate enough to present the compressive response of the core under quasi static compressive load.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Compressive deformation process of the core

Taking the CFRP honeycomb core with $l_w=10$ mm and filled with PMI foam blocks of the density $\rho_f=75$ kg/m³ for instance, the quasi static compressive deformation process of is presented in Fig. 6.

As discussed above, the deformation process of the core with $\varepsilon_n \leq 0.15$ can be divided into four stages, i.e. the linear elastic stage ($0 < \varepsilon_n < 0.016$), the buckling stage ($0.016 \leq \varepsilon_n < 0.026$), the failure stage ($0.026 \leq \varepsilon_n < 0.046$) and the plateau stage ($\varepsilon_n \geq 0.046$). During the first stage, as shown in Fig. 6(a), the core was linearly compressed in the z direction and no plastic damage occurred in this stage. With the the increase of the nominal strain, the honeycomb walls buckled at the nominal strain of $\varepsilon_n=0.016$, which can be seen in Fig. 6 (b) and the increasing rate of the stress decreased accordingly duo the decrease in material stiffness. Then the stress reached its peak value at the nominal strain of $\varepsilon_n=0.026$ and at this point the failure of the honeycomb initiated; it can be seen from Fig. 6 (c) that the damage variable reached to the value of 1 and bending deformation can be observed in the honeycomb walls. The honeycomb then collapsed and the stress dropped to a nearly plateau value and with the compressive process continued, cracks appeared in the damage zones and folding of the honeycomb walls can be observed in Fig. 6 (d) and (e).

Fig. 6 Compressive deformation process of the core

4.2 Energy absorption process of the core

Fig. 7 shows the energy absorption process of the core with $l_w=10$ mm and $\rho_f=75$ kg/m³, including the contribution of the CFRP honeycomb and foam fillers, as well as the deformation of the foam fillers shown as equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) at two specific nominal strain.

It can be seen that before the honeycomb failed, the energy absorption of the core is dominated by the honeycomb. It is because that during this stage, no plastic deformation occurred in foam fillers. After the honeycomb failed, the plastic deformation of the foam fillers showed up gradually under the effects of the compressive loading and honeycomb deformation. Consequently, energy absorbed by

the foam fillers increased with the increase of the nominal strain so that the contribution of the foam fillers increased. Overall, the energy absorbed by the foam fillers is much fewer than that by the honeycomb.

Fig. 7 Energy absorption process of the core with $l_w=10$ mm and $\rho_f=75$ kg/m³

4.3 Effects of h_c on the compressive response

To analyze the effects of the core height on the compressive response of this hybrid core structure, we simulated the compression of the hybrid cores with fixed spacing between honeycomb walls ($l_w=10$ mm) and foam density ($\rho_f=75$ kg/m³) and different core heights (h_c). The compressive nominal stress versus nominal strain curves of the hybrid cores, of which the core height is 10 mm, 20 mm, 30 mm, and 50 mm, respectively, are shown in Fig. 8.

We can see from Fig. 8 that the core height has no effect on the linear elastic response and buckling initiation of the hybrid core. However, the peak stress and the plateau stress of the core were affected by the core height. Specifically, with the increase of the core height, the peak stress decreased while the plateau stress increased. The decrease of the peak stress is due to the reduction in the stability of the honeycomb walls with the increase of the core height, which lead to earlier initiation of the core failure. The increase of the plateau stress is because that the compressive displacement increases with the increase of core height at a certain nominal strain. Thus, the deformation of foam fillers became severe and thus the plateau stress increased.

Fig. 8 σ_n - ϵ_n curves of hybrid cores with different core height ($l_w=10$ mm, $\rho_f=75$ kg/m³)

Fig. 9 shows the specific energy absorption of hybrid cores with different core heights. It indicates that before the core failed, the specific energy absorption of hybrid cores was not affected by the core height. The difference in specific energy absorption showed up after the core failed. With the increase of the core height, the specific energy absorption also increased, providing that cores with larger heights are more energy efficient. However, the mass increase must be taken into consideration when trying to improve the energy efficiency of the core by increasing its height.

Fig. 9 Specific energy absorption of hybrid cores with different core heights

4.4 Effects of l_w on the compressive response

The compressive stress versus strain relations of the hybrid core with different l_w is shown in Fig. 10. It can be seen that with the increase of the spacing, the elastic modulus, the peak stress as well as the plateau stress of the core decreased, which means that the increase of l_w leads to the decrease in the stiffness and strength of the core.

Fig. 10 σ_n - ϵ_n curves of hybrid cores with different spacing between honeycomb walls

The specific energy absorption of hybrid cores with different l_w is presented in Fig. 11. It can be seen that the specific energy absorption increased with the decrease of l_w . Additionally, the increasing rate of the specific energy absorption of the core with l_w became larger as l_w decreased. Specifically, when l_w changed from 25 mm to 20 mm, the specific energy absorption of the core had no obvious change. However, there was a significant increase of the specific energy absorption when l_w decreased from 15 mm to 10 mm.

Fig. 11 Specific energy absorption of hybrid cores with different l_w

4.5 Effects of PMI foam fillers on the compressive response

Simulations on the compression of empty honeycomb and honeycombs with PMI foam fillers of which the densities are 52 kg/m^3 , 75 kg/m^3 and 110 kg/m^3 were conducted, respectively and the σ_n - ε_n curves are shown in Fig. 12. We can see that the foam fillers have a significant effect on the peak stress and plateau stress of the core. Specifically, the foam fillers can improve the stability of the honeycomb, thus the buckling failure of the honeycomb walls occurred at a larger nominal strain and the peak stress increased accordingly. Additionally, with the increase of the foam density, the peak stress and the plateau stress were also increased.

Fig. 12 σ_n - ε_n curves of empty honeycomb and honeycombs with foam fillers of different densities

Fig. 13 shows the specific energy absorption of the honeycomb core and hybrid cores with different foam fillers. It can be seen from Fig. 13 that the foam fillers dramatically improved the energy efficiency of the honeycomb core. Furthermore, the specific energy absorption of the hybrid core also increased with the increase of the foam density, but the difference between three types of hybrid cores in specific energy absorption was not significant.

Fig. 13 Specific energy absorption of the honeycomb core and hybrid cores with different foam fillers

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Square CFRP honeycomb cores with PMI foam fillers were proposed and prepared. The quasi static compressive properties of the core were analyzed by compressive tests and numerical simulations. The PMI foam fillers significantly improved the compressive properties of the CFRP honeycomb by increasing the compressive strength and specific energy absorption efficiency.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by Postgraduate Research & Practice Innovation Program of Jiangsu Province (KYCX18_0474).

REFERENCES

- [1] B. P. Russell, V. S. Deshpande and H. N. G. Wadley, Quasistatic deformation and failure modes of composite square honeycombs, *Journal of Mechanics of Materials and Structures*, **3**, 2008, pp 1315-1340.
- [2] B. P. Russell, T. Liu, N. A. Fleck and V. S. Deshpande, Quasi-static three-point bending of carbon fiber sandwich beams with square honeycomb cores, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, **78**, 2011, pp 031008-1-15.
- [3] B. P. Russell, T. Liu, N. A. Fleck and V. S. Deshpande, The soft impact of composite sandwich beams with a square-honeycomb core, *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, **48**, 2012, pp 65-81.
- [4] Y. Hu, W. Li, X. An and H. Fan, Fabrication and mechanical behaviors of corrugated lattice truss composite sandwich panels, *Composites Science and Technology*, **125**, 2016, pp 114-122.
- [5] T. Y. Reddy and R. J. Wall, Axial compression of foam-filled thin-walled circular tubes, *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, **7**, 1988, pp 151-166.
- [6] C. Wu, C. Weeks and C. Sun, Improving honeycomb-core sandwich structures for impact resistance, *Journal of Advanced Materials*, **26**, 1995, pp 41-47.
- [7] H. Mazafari, H. Molatefi, V. Crupi, G. Epasto and E. Guglielmino, In plane compressive response and crushing of foam filled aluminum honeycombs, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **49**, 2015, pp 3215-3228.
- [8] Q. Liu, J. Fu, J. Wang, J. Ma, H. Chen, Q. Li and D. Hui, Axial and lateral crushing responses of aluminum honeycombs filled with EPP foam, *Composites Part B*, **130**, 2017, pp 236-247.
- [9] Y. Zhang, Q. Liu, Z. He, Z. Zong and J. Fang, Dynamic impact response of aluminum honeycombs filled with Expanded Polypropylene foam, *Composites Part B*, **156**, 2019, pp 17-27.
- [10] PMI foam cores find further applications, *Reinforced Plastics*, **44**, 2000, pp 36-38.
- [11] ABAQUS/Explicit User's manual. Version 6.7. Hibbitt, Karlsson & Sorensen Inc., Pawtucket, 2008.
- [12] H. Zhou, T. Liu, R. Guo, R. Liu and P. Song, Numerical investigation on water blast response of freestanding carbon fiber reinforced composite sandwich plates with square honeycomb cores, *Applied Composite Materials*, **26**, 2018, pp 605-625.
- [13] V. S. Deshpande and N. A. Fleck, Multi-axial yield behaviour of polymer foams, *Acta Materialia*, **49**, 2001, pp 1859-1866.